

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036640.

Accelerating the transition to sustainable mobility in schools

Part of the Collection: Findings and Recommendations
from the SHARED GREEN DEAL Social Experiments

June 2025

Nadine Haufe • Andrea Tönkö

Accelerating the transition to sustainable mobility in schools

Part of the Collection: Findings and Recommendations from
the SHARED GREEN DEAL Social Experiments

June 2025

Thomas Reibnegger

Nadine Haufe*

TU Wien
Austria

Andrea Tönkö

Metropolitan Research Institute
Hungary

* Corresponding author:
nadine.haufe@tuwien.ac.at

Suggested citation

Haufe, N., Tönkö, A., 2025. *Accelerating the transition to sustainable mobility in schools*. In: Robison, R. and Royston, S. (eds.): Findings and Recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL Social Experiments. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15315291>

Executive summary of recommendations

This report presents findings of the social experiments on Sustainable Mobility within the SHARED GREEN DEAL project. Urban Mobility Labs were created within schools in four European cities – Sofia (Bulgaria), Panevėžys (Lithuania), Braga (Portugal) and Galway (Ireland). Each Lab involved young people and stakeholders such as teachers, parents and school administrators from three schools. The recommendations from these experiments target promotion of sustainable mobility in schools, infrastructure improvements, and accelerating the transition to sustainable mobility as per the European Green Deal.

Recommendations for promoting sustainable mobility within schools

- **Integrate sustainable mobility into curricula:** Embedding mobility topics through subjects like Citizenship or Environmental Science helps encourage behavioural change. Active learning experiences such as competitions, workshops and field projects help engage students in real-world sustainability challenges. Such initiatives can challenge institutional norms around mobility, fostering long-term cultural change.
- **Support school mobility projects:** Programmes like ‘Walk-to-School’, cycling campaigns, and step challenges can encourage students to incorporate more physical activity into their daily routines. Additionally, supporting student-led mobility initiatives helps raise awareness and boost engagement.

Recommendations for sustainable mobility infrastructure

- **Enhance safe and sustainable infrastructure:** Investments in pedestrian and cycling infrastructure around schools – including wider sidewalks, protected bike lanes, and improved street lighting – can make active travel a safer and more attractive option. Traffic-calming measures, such as lower speed limits in school zones, further enhance road safety.
- **Optimise public and school transport systems:** Collaborate with public transport providers to improve accessibility by ensuring well-connected routes, affordable fare structures, and safe, convenient transit options for students. Promote subsidised or discounted fare programs for students.
- **Improve accessibility and inclusion:** Ensure that all students, especially those from socially disadvantaged families, have access to sustainable transport). Infrastructure improvements, including wheelchair-accessible paths, tactile paving, and safer pedestrian crossings, are essential to making mobility inclusive for all.

Recommendations for wider policy on school mobility

- **Foster co-creative multi-generational engagement:** Efforts which involve students, parents, and the wider community are most effective. Organising family-oriented activities and fostering dialogue between generations can support cultural shifts. Supporting youth participation in decision-making processes strengthens their sense of ownership and responsibility toward sustainable mobility.
- **Promote sustainable mobility through legal and regulatory frameworks:** Establishing clear legal frameworks and municipal policies is essential to support infrastructure and programmes including safe cycling routes, pedestrian-friendly school zones, and accessible public transport options. Strengthening regulations to limit car traffic around schools, enforcing low-emission zones, and prioritising sustainable transport modes in urban planning are crucial in fostering a greener mobility culture.
- **Raise awareness of sustainable mobility:** Public awareness campaigns should highlight the benefits of sustainable school mobility choices, emphasising environmental, health, and community advantages. Utilising social media, student-led advocacy, and community events can amplify these messages, making them more visible and engaging.
- **Demonstrate concrete actions and commitment:** Sustainable school mobility initiatives must lead to tangible results, as visible progress is the main driving force for young people to engage and take an active role in such projects. Implementing concrete measures demonstrates commitment and reinforces the impact of sustainability efforts.

■ List of Contents

1. Introduction	5
1.1. The SHARED GREEN DEAL Project.....	5
1.2. Policy context for the Sustainable Mobility experiments	5
1.3. Aim of the Sustainable Mobility experiments	6
2. The social experiment	7
2.1. Social experiment design.....	7
2.2. Social institutions: meso phenomena for the Sustainable Mobility experiments	8
2.3. Participants in the experiments	9
2.4. Outcomes of the Sustainable Mobility Experiments.....	10
2.5. Data collection methods	13
3. Transformations in social institutions	14
3.1. Impacts on participants' awareness	14
3.2. Impacts on participants' behaviours	15
3.3. Barriers to sustainable school travel	15
3.4. Wider scale and infrastructural impacts of the experiment.....	16
3.5. Sociotechnical evolution.....	16
3.6. Impacts on social institutions.....	17
4. Learning points and recommendations for policy and governance	19
4.1. Successes and learning points of the experiments.....	19
4.2. Recommendations for fostering sustainable mobility projects in schools.....	22
4.3. Policy recommendations.....	25
4.3.1. Recommendations for promoting sustainable mobility within schools	25
4.3.2. Recommendations for sustainable mobility infrastructure	25
4.3.3. Recommendations for wider policy on school mobility.....	26
5. Conclusions	28
6. Acknowledgements	30
7. References	31
Appendix – Methods	32
A1. Data collection	32
A2. Coding process.....	33

■ List of Figures

<i>Figure 2.1. Experiment Design</i>	8
<i>Figure A2. Steps of inductive category development</i>	34

■ List of Boxes

Box 1. What is meant by social institutions in the Sustainable Mobility Experiments?	8
---	----------

■ List of Tables

<i>Table 2.3. Number and gender of formal members of forums</i>	9
<i>Table 2.5. Number and gender of interviewees</i>	13
<i>Table A1.a. Number of interviews and interview duration per experimental location</i>	32
<i>Table A1.b. Interviewee characteristics in each experiment location</i>	33

1. Introduction

1.1. The SHARED GREEN DEAL Project

This report presents findings on Sustainable Mobility as part of the Horizon 2020 project “*Social sciences and Humanities for Achieving a Responsible, Equitable and Desirable Green Deal*” (SHARED GREEN DEAL). The EU Green Deal is a programme of policies aimed at overcoming climate change and environmental degradation by transforming the EU into a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy. The goal of SHARED GREEN DEAL is to stimulate behavioural, social and cultural change across Europe, aligned with the policy priorities of the Green Deal.

SHARED GREEN DEAL provides Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) tools to support the implementation of the Green Deal programme. In the past, SSH research on green transitions has focussed on changes to either individuals (‘micro’ phenomena) or systems and collectives (‘macro’ phenomena). In contrast, SHARED GREEN DEAL focuses on ‘middle range’ (‘meso’) changes to bridge these two sets of understandings and priorities (Foulds et al., 2025). Using this innovative ‘meso’ approach, the project links societal actors to foster knowledge sharing, learn from collective experiences, and feed back into ‘macro’ policies and governance.

The SHARED GREEN DEAL consortium brings together 22 leading organisations from across Europe, including universities, research institutions, network organisations and businesses. The project is structured around six priority Green Deal topics: Clean Energy, Circular Economy, Efficient Renovations, Sustainable Mobility, Sustainable Food, and Preserving Biodiversity. Within these six themes, a total of 24 social experiments have been delivered across different EU member states and affiliated countries, working with local municipalities and not-for-profit organisations¹. Alongside this Report on sustainable mobility, there are five further Reports, on the other five priority Green Deal topics of the project². Other resources related to the running of and impacts from the social experiments can also be found via www.sharedgreendeal.eu.

1.2. Policy context for the Sustainable Mobility experiments

The mobility transition is playing a key role in shaping numerous current challenges in climate change adaptation. The European Green Deal (EC, 2019) is addressing these issues in several ways, such as by emphasising the aim to achieve a “90% reduction in transport emissions by 2050” (EC 2019, p.10). Moreover, it stresses that “Transport should become drastically less polluting, especially in cities. A combination of measures should address emissions, urban congestion, and improved public transport” (EC, 2019, p.11).

1 Further detail about each of the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments can be found in the project’s Case Study Guides (Kovács et al., 2024).

2 All reports can be accessed here: www.sharedgreendeal.eu/expt-findings

However, the Green Deal also stresses that “New measures on their own will not be enough to achieve the European Green Deal’s objectives” (EC, 2019, p.4). In this sense, achieving sustainable transport means “putting users first” (EC, 2019, p.10) by providing them with alternatives to their current mobility habits and also ensuring that these are affordable, accessible, safe, cleaner, and comfortable. In this context, the European Commission points out that also public and private organisation, such as schools, should be encouraged to develop mobility actions that promote low- and zero-emission transportation means (EC, 2021, p. 21). Therefore, within SHARED GREEN DEAL, this experiment stream focuses on sustainable urban mobility, especially in schools.

1.3. Aim of the Sustainable Mobility experiments

The social experiments on Sustainable Mobility focus on social institutions (the ‘meso unit’ for this experimental stream), understood as “systems of interconnected norms that are rooted in shared values and generalised within a particular society or social group as shared ways of acting, thinking and feeling” (Ritzer, 2006, p. 90). We have intervened in these social institutions through creating local Urban Mobility Labs (Franta et al., 2018), which can be understood as a specific testing environment in ‘real life’, where citizens are involved in the design, testing, co-creation and adoption of new solutions in the transport and mobility sector.

School-related mobility has an important impact on the urban mobility system and is an important driver of children’s and young people’s health and behaviours around mobility (e.g. Fusco et al., 2012; Waygood et al., 2017; EC, 2021). However, schools also bring together different people from the wider community and are thus excellent ‘hubs’ for collective change (Horelli, 1998). Through the creation of Urban Mobility Labs in schools, we have attempted to intervene in social institutions (including values and norms) in the context of school travel to support the Green Deal objective of accelerating the transition to sustainable and intelligent mobility.

The experiments took place in four different European cities: Braga (Portugal), Galway (Ireland), Panevėžys (Lithuania), and Sofia (Bulgaria) over the course of one year. Each experiment was specific to the local context and addressed the local challenges and needs of school mobility. However, all four experiments had the following objectives:

- Develop future mobility strategies through local Urban Mobility Labs in schools.
- Co-create context-specific interventions (e.g. games, exhibitions, educational materials, small physical interventions) to disrupt and evolve institutionalised norms and raise awareness about sustainable school mobility.
- Formulate city-level policy recommendations for school travel strategies, thereby promoting the representation of young people in policy-making and planning processes.
- Support the EU Green Deal objective of sustainable and intelligent mobility.

In order to present the findings of the SHARED GREEN DEAL Sustainable Mobility Experiments, this report is divided into five sections. Following this introduction (Section 1), Section 2 outlines what happened in the experiment. Section 3 presents our findings on the changes in social institutions that occurred as a result of the experiment. Section 4 provides learning points and recommendations for policy and governance. Section 5 concludes with reflections on the findings, implications e.g. for governance and for further research and similar work in other contexts.

2. The social experiment

2.1. Social experiment design

SHARED GREEN DEAL supported the creation of Urban Mobility Labs within schools in 4 European cities—Sofia (Bulgaria) and Panevėžys (Lithuania), Braga (Portugal) and Galway (Ireland). Each Urban Mobility Lab involved young people (aged 10-18) and stakeholders such as teachers, parents and school administrators from three schools. The labs included eight forums in each location where young people and adults worked together in a co-creative environment to promote sustainable school mobility.

The one-year co-creative participation process of the experiments started in May 2023. It consisted of three phases (see Figure 2.1):

- **Phase 1–Co-Identification:**
In the first phase, the local mobility problems and needs in related to school transport were identified and collected. In the beginning, both the young participants (Youth Mobility Check Forum) and the stakeholders (Stakeholder Mobility Check Forum) collected the problems, needs and ideas in separate forums. Then young people and stakeholders discussed and merged the problems, needs and ideas together (Synthesis Forum).
- **Phase 2 – Co-Selection and Co-Preparation:**
During this phase, the identified problems and needs were prioritised and first solutions prepared for implementation (Field of Action Forum). An initial list of policy recommendations was also formulated, reflecting the collective input from participants (Youth Mobility Policy Forum).
- **Phase 3 – Co-Development and Co-Implementation:**
The final phase focused on developing and implementing the selected solutions. Additionally, policy recommendations were validated and finalised based on feedback from participants (Youth Design Forums I and II). Finally, the policy recommendations and solutions developed were presented to a wider audience (Final Forum).

Special emphasis was placed on the involvement of young people at all stages of the experiment to ensure that their perspectives were included in addressing the challenges of school mobility. Age-appropriate, playful methods such as field trips, games, online tools and workshops were used to work together with adults on future mobility strategies, context-specific interventions (e.g. games, exhibitions, educational materials, small physical interventions) and to formulate city-level policy recommendations for school travel strategies.

Figure 2.1. Experiment Design

2.2. Social institutions: meso phenomena for the Sustainable Mobility experiments

Box 1. What is meant by social institutions in the Sustainable Mobility Experiments?

We define social institutions with reference to the sociological concept of institutions. In contrast to a colloquial understanding of institutions as individual organisations (e.g. schools), a sociological understanding refers to the “*systems of interrelated norms that are rooted in shared values and are generalised across a particular society or social group as its common ways of acting, thinking, and feeling*” (Ritzer, 2006, p.90). These norms are context dependent and relatively dynamic in the sense that they differ between places and change throughout time. However, they interact with the macro phenomena of political, economic and legal structures and material infrastructures and the micro phenomena of individual behaviour and preferences. In this sense, social institutions are a meso unit (Rageth et al., 2021), forming a middle ground between individual practices and larger societal structures and material infrastructures.

The mobility experiments in the four cities aimed to intervene in meso phenomena between micro and macro, i.e. the social institutions underlying school mobility, by developing context-specific future mobility strategies.

The ‘future mobility strategies’ that emerged from the experiments were translated into policy recommendations for sustainable school mobility as well as context-specific interventions (e.g. games, school mobility plans, small physical interventions, etc.) that targeted and disrupted institutionalised ways of acting, thinking and feeling.

The development of such ‘mobility strategies’ often still follows top-down planning approaches and

is led by professional (adult) planners. However, the planning process can also be understood as a ‘communicative practice’ (e.g. Healey, 1992) where the development of desirable solutions requires not only expert knowledge but also local and situated knowledge (Haufe and Franta 2020, p.164-165). This is particularly relevant for young people, who are often not fully recognised “as critical stakeholders in their cities...to provide insightful local knowledge to inform practices and strategies for planning cities” (McKoy, Eppley, and Buss 2022, p.45). For this reason, the mobility experiments in the SHARED GREEN DEAL project emphasised the role of young people as experts on their own mobility contexts and actively involved them in all stages of the co-creation process of the mobility experiments.

2.3. Participants in the experiments

A total of 165 people made up the formal membership of the forums of the SHARED GREEN DEAL mobility experiments in the four locations (see Table 2.3, which also shows participants’ genders³).

Table 2.3. Number and gender of formal members of forums.

Location	Members	Number ⁴	Women and girls	Men and boys
Sofia (Bulgaria)	Young people	33	21	12
	Adult stakeholders	14	13	1
Total		47	34	13
Braga (Portugal)	Young people	18	13	5
	Adult stakeholders	16	11	5
Total		34	24	10
Panevėžys (Lithuania)	Young people	39	31	8
	Adult stakeholders	13	12	1
Total		52	43	9
Galway (Ireland)	Young people	26	18	8
	Adult stakeholders	6	4	2
Total		32	22	10
Total number of formal members in all four locations		165	123	42

A total of 116 young people and 49 adult stakeholders (mainly teachers and parents) therefore worked together to develop context-specific future mobility strategies in the SHARED GREEN DEAL Sustainable Mobility experiments in the four cities.

3 When collecting data on participants’ genders, we asked them to self-identify. We report genders using the terms “man/boy”, “woman/girl” and “non-binary”, in accordance with World Health Organisation guidance on sex and gender terminology. See: <https://www.who.int/health-topics/gender>

4 Only young people and adult stakeholders who were formal members of the forums (i.e. with parentally-signed or adult member consent forms) are included in this table. However additional young people participated in some of the activities as part of their school day, which parents were informed of, and additional adults participated in some of the activities.

2.4. Outcomes of the Sustainable Mobility Experiments

The ‘future mobility strategies’ that emerged from the experiments were translated into policy recommendations for sustainable school mobility as well as context-specific interventions that targeted and disrupted institutionalised ways of acting, thinking and feeling.

Each Urban Mobility Lab formulated policy recommendations for school travel strategies at the city level, fostering youth representation in policymaking and planning processes. Key issues addressed included:

- Bike and pedestrian infrastructure
- Public transport
- School travel safety and dangerous parking
- Gender and cycling considerations

Each Urban Mobility Lab also co-created context-specific solutions, understood as interventions to disrupt institutionalised ways of acting, thinking and feeling:

Panevėžys Lab:

- Tested a sustainable mobility game for schools.
- Developed school travel plans for each school.
- Created guidelines for other schools to develop travel plans.

Braga Lab:

- Created periscopes to experience the impact of cars from children’s perspective.
- Increased the number of guardians using public transport.
- Reduced parking spaces in front of the school.

Sofia Lab:

- Developed a ‘My Dream to Go to School’ mailbox system to gather school mobility habits, needs, and ideas to propose and implement new alternatives for children to get to school.
- Created a communication channel between students, teachers and principals to strengthen the voice of young people in schools.

Galway Lab:

- Conducted a survey and walkability audits.
- Closed the road in front of the schools for half a day.
- Used a drone to document space usage by 30 students travelling by bus, bike, or car.

◀ Mobility game & developing School Travel Plans in Panevėžys (Lithuania), Credits: ECAT

▶ Preparing post-boxes for 'My Dream to Go to School' in Sofia (Bulgaria), Credits: Sofia Development Association

2.5. Data collection methods

To collect process-related data (e.g. strengths and challenges of the experiments) and impact-related data (e.g. main achievements, changes in mobility practices, knowledge and meanings, organisational changes) qualitative interviews were carried out in all four locations. The interviews took place between March and May 2024. 42 interviews were conducted with participants, i.e. young people and adults (parents and teachers) in the experiments. These interviews were conducted individually or in pairs. Four additional interviews were conducted with local partners, i.e. the facilitators of the experiments in each location. A total of 56 people were interviewed: 32 young people and 24 adults (parents, teachers and local partners). In total, 39 of the interviewees were women or girls and 17 were men or boys.

The local partners conducted the interviews with the experiment participants, and the SHARED GREEN DEAL consortium partners conducted the interviews with the local partners. The interviews lasted from 13 to 95 minutes. Table 2.5 shows the number and gender of interviewees per location and in total.

Table 2.5. Number and gender of interviewees.

Location	Interviewee	Number	Women and girls	Men and boys
Sofia (Bulgaria: BG)	Young people	8	3	5
	Adults	6	6	0
Total		14	9	5
Braga (Portugal: PT)	Young people	9	5	4
	Adults	8	7	1
Total		17	12	5
Panevėžys (Lithuania: LT)	Young people	6	4	2
	Adults	5	5	0
Total		11	9	2
Galway (Ireland: IE)	Young people	9	6	3
	Adults	5	3	2
Total		14	9	5
Total number of interviewees in all four locations		56	39	17

Data analysis was based on Mayring's (2014, 2015) approach to qualitative content analysis (QCA, see Appendix). The coding process was carried out using MAXQDA software.

When quoting from our interview transcripts, we do not use names, to protect participants' identities. We have chosen to include participants' role category (labelled: Parents, Teachers, Young people, Local partners) and gender category (labelled: Men/boys; or Women/girls) as these are important characteristics for us in contextualising our data and claims. In the remainder of the report, quotes from interviews will be labelled as follows: [Country Code Unique interview number, Role category, Gender category]. In some cases, quotes are slightly paraphrased (rather than verbatim) for clarity and concision.

3. Transformations in social institutions

The experiments in the four locations aimed to intervene in the meso phenomena of social institutions underlying school mobility by developing context-specific mobility strategies within Urban Mobility Labs. Our data analysis shows that the development of context-specific future mobility strategies in Urban Mobility Labs in schools can lead to impacts on different phenomena (micro, macro and meso). The following subsections present the impacts of the experiments on participants' awareness of sustainable school mobility (3.1), and mobility behaviours (3.2), as well as barriers to sustainable school mobility (3.3). Wider scale and infrastructural impacts of the experiment (3.4), and results on how materials/technologies influenced social outcomes and vice versa (socio-technical evolution) (3.5), are also presented before we discuss key impacts on social institutions (3.6).

3.1. Impacts on participants' awareness

Our data shows that the development of context-specific mobility strategies in Urban Mobility Labs in schools can promote reflection and thinking about the 'norms and values institutionalised in society' in relation to (school) mobility. Many of the young people interviewed stated that the experiments had made them think and learn a lot about sustainable mobility, road safety, the environment and the impact of cars on society, the environment and health. The young people interviewed also said that the experiments had given them a different view of mobility, the environment and the world, and had made them more sensitive to others and also changed their opinion about using cars.

"We've always gone by car...now with the project, it's given us a bit more to think about." [PT02, Young people, Women/girls]

"It changed my mind about using a car to [go to] school because now I understand that it releases carbon dioxide, it fogs up the air, which gives us breathing problems." [BG01, Young people, Men/boys]

"I was like: Oh I always either cycle or walk, but [now I] look at how that's not something everyone can do, and...why they wouldn't want to, or why...it's just not possible." [IE03, Young people, Women/girls]

The adult participants in the experiments who were interviewed also stated that the experiment and the work with the young people had made them think and changed their view of everyday school mobility.

"I still drive to school but I definitely have way more of an awareness of cyclists and pedestrians around me... it's just given me that better understanding." [IE02, Teachers, Women/girls]

3.2. Impacts on participants' behaviours

In addition to raising awareness of sustainable school mobility, the interviews showed that Urban Mobility Labs in schools and the development of context-specific mobility strategies can lead to behavioural changes. For example, there are some teachers who, as a result of the experiment, walk more, use public transport more often or use the car less. Young people also talked about behavioural changes on their way to school. Some now cycle to school, others walk more instead of driving to school with their parents, walk to school with others, have started to use public transport or carpool more often.

"I found suitable-for-me public transport routes... this really happened just because of the project. Before I was driving a car daily. I didn't even think that I could travel to my working place differently. ...Wow, I've changed my movement 100%". [LT01, Teachers, Women/girls]

"I think some effects have emerged. I can see now that people are telling me, 'Oh, now I come by bike,' and I'm happy to hear that." [PT02, Young people, Women/girls]

3.3. Barriers to sustainable school travel

However, other respondents stated that they were unable to change their behaviour because of barriers. Some teachers and parents talked about family commitments or working conditions as barriers to behaviour change towards more sustainable modes of transport.

"Oh, I bring so much stuff to school, between books and coffee, I wouldn't be able to cycle in and I've got 10 bags coming in with me every morning. I don't think it would be feasible for me to cycle in either, yeah, I'll probably just drive because I've other commitments..." [IE02, Teachers, Women/girls]

"To a certain extent, yes, the children in a way have made us think about the problems that exist. But on the other hand... as parents and with the commitments that we have, the workload, it's harder and harder for us to...try to follow that model, the good model." [BG08, Parents, Women/girls]

Barriers to sustainable school travel were also mentioned by some of the young people. The main barriers to changing young people's mobility behaviour were identified as distance to school, integration of school travel into family life, weather conditions, heavy school bags, gender norms, lack of road safety and parental concerns.

"I end up coming to school by car every day. My mum drives, there are four of us in the car, my sister also attends this school, and they bring us to school every morning... And as soon as they drop us off at school, they go straight to work, so it's always just one journey." [PT03, Young people, Women/girls]

"My child wanted to go cycling. But when I explained to him that it's quite far and he has to carry his backpack and get up early anyway, his enthusiasm passed." [BG03, Parents, Women/girls]

3.4. Wider scale and infrastructural impacts of the experiment

In terms of macro changes, the interviews show that Urban Mobility Labs in schools and the development of context-specific mobility strategies have also brought about changes in schools. Inspired by the experiments, discussions on active and sustainable school mobility started in the participating schools. Ideas on how to include sustainable mobility in the curriculum were discussed and ideas for initiatives (such as clubs and activities related to sustainability) were developed.

“It definitely started conversations and it put active and sustainable transport on the agenda.”
[IE12, Local partners, Men/boys]

“In one of the schools the experiment actually started the discussion of having dedicated lessons for sustainable and sustainability topics. Also, to find ways to plant more trees along the school. In the other school they actually... decided that they will also work on environmental issues during these meetings [where students choose the study topics]. And the third school, from them came the idea to create a sustainability group at school that will be a voluntary club of students that will do different activities related to sustainability. Either a recycling class or workshop or some other kinds of activity.” [BG11, Local partners, Women/girls]

In terms of infrastructure changes, respondents reported only a few measures around the schools, mainly in Braga, e.g. changes in bus timetables, and a new pedestrian crossing in front of one school:

“A pedestrian crossing in front of [a participating] secondary school, which had already been requested for two years. The request had not been answered at all. So that was a victory and something that really encouraged the students to continue participating, because...they truly felt that their difficulties and suggestions had been taken into account, and so that adds value to their work and their position.” [PT07, Teachers, Women/girls]

The majority of respondents did not notice any changes in the infrastructure around their school as a result of the experiment. However, infrastructure/environmental changes are seen by many as important, but also as “hard to change” [BG03, Parents, Women/girls].

As one summed up: “Absolutely need the infrastructure to change first” [IE09, Young people, Men/boys].

3.5. Sociotechnical evolution

Our analysis also explored socio-technical evolution, i.e. how technologies/ materials/ infrastructures influence social outcomes and vice versa. The implementation of a pedestrian crossing in front of a school in Braga shows that the results of social experiments such as the Urban Mobility Labs in schools can lead to changes in the material environment. These are important for the transition to sustainable school mobility, as the interviews show. For example, the young people interviewed are well aware of the importance of the built environment, and for the local partner from Galway, changes to the infrastructure are an indispensable prerequisite for the social outcome of behavioural changes towards more sustainable mobility.

“We’re still at the Stage One of hard infrastructure change, and behavioural change has to follow that. There’s no point in focusing on telling people that they need to change their behaviour if the infrastructure isn’t there for them.” [IE12, Local partners, Men/boys]

“In our neighbourhood and in other neighbourhoods a lot of kids don’t go out because it’s not as green, there’s no playgrounds, the sidewalks are broken, they have potholes, there’s cars parked everywhere, there’s a lot of cars going by and I think that so much traffic sometimes prevents kids from playing.” [BG05, Young people, Women/girls]

Rather than digital innovations or major structural changes, many respondents would like to see small adjustments such as more bike racks and larger lockers at schools, wider and more intact pavements, more pedestrian crossings for a safe route to school, more cycle paths, less litter on the street, and more flowers and plants on the way to school.

3.6. Impacts on social institutions

In summary, the experiments in the four locations aimed to intervene in the meso phenomena of social institutions underlying school mobility. Overall, our analysis shows that interventions or changes in ‘common acting, thinking and feeling’ are possible through the development of context-specific strategies in Urban Mobility Labs in schools. However, the local partners make it clear that the ‘norms and values institutionalised in society’ (meso phenomena), such as the ‘car culture’, represent a major challenge for sustainable school mobility, which will not be easy to overcome in the short term.

“As this problem is deeply rooted in the society, we are aware that the changes to a sustainable system will be a process of adaptation that will be difficult to achieve in the short term. However, any progress is very important and we believe that the school community and especially this Mobility Lab group will be important ambassadors for influencing the entire school community in Braga.” [PT12, Local partners, Women/girls]

“Car culture... it was mentioned that boards of management in schools would often be pro-car and would like greater car parks and wouldn’t be so interested or bothered about having cycle lanes or bus stops. Their priority would be providing for car drivers.” [IE, Local partners, Men/boys]

Although the implementation of Urban Mobility Labs in schools and the involvement of different groups is seen as a challenge by some local partners, all local partners believe that through a well implemented co-creation project, even those who are sceptical of cultural change can contribute to sustainable solutions and behaviour change.

“What we learned is that it’s possible to do everything, if you work. Because really at the beginning, we couldn’t imagine that we would pass all these eight forums and that we would succeed in keeping interest from schools and from the municipality. And we did that. So again, just do and just be enthusiastic.” [LT11, Local partners, Women/girls]

“The most important lesson was to learn that changes are possible and that in a... co-creation project like this, even the most sceptical about cultural change can contribute to sustainable solutions and change behaviour.” [PT, Local partners, Women/girls]

In addition, all respondents consider initiatives with future generations to be a very important and relevant component for initiating and achieving changes towards more sustainable school mobility and a shift in socially institutionalised norms and values (meso phenomena).

“By getting young people actively involved in their surroundings, in their community, in their municipality, they’ll surely become more aware citizens and then pass it on to others.” [PT06, Teachers, Women/girls]

“It was a really nice experience and after this, I came to the personal realisation that if we would like to continue working on sustainability projects, we have to actually work more and more with kids, in order to be successful.” [BG11, Local partners, Women/girls]

Overall therefore, respondents reported changes in their own awareness and behaviour towards sustainable mobility, as well as increased attention on the cultural elements which underlie mobility patterns. This suggests that developing contextual strategies in school Urban Mobility Labs can impact on social institutions, i.e. the way certain social groups act, think and feel together.

Furthermore, institutional norms and values such as ‘car culture’ are inscribed not only in individual practices but also in the material environment, such as the urban mobility system and the school system. Thus, the respondents make it clear that a change in school mobility and the underlying institutional values and norms is not possible without a change in the infrastructure or material environment (macro phenomena). Unsafe school routes, missing bus routes or heavy backpacks lead to the reproduction of unsustainable social institutions and thus hinder changes towards sustainable school mobility. In this context, Urban Mobility Labs in schools offer an opportunity to broaden the perspective to macro phenomena, but changes in the infrastructure or material environment of school mobility require the involvement of other actors such as urban planners, transport planners, school administrators, etc. in order to initiate sustainable changes in social institutions.

4. Learning points and recommendations for policy and governance

The SHARED GREEN DEAL mobility experiments intervened in the meso phenomena of social institutions (including values and norms) underlying school mobility by developing context-specific mobility strategies within Urban Mobility Labs in schools. In the previous section we showed that Urban Mobility Labs in schools are a good way to initiate change, but that there are also barriers that can hinder change towards sustainable school mobility. This section provides learning points and recommendations for policymakers and implementers to replicate similar initiatives. By understanding the factors that contribute to success and the challenges encountered, stakeholders can design strategies that foster a culture of sustainability.

4.1. Successes and learning points of the experiments

Involvement and engagement

Engagement emerged as a pivotal factor in the success of the sustainable mobility experiments. The active participation of diverse stakeholders, including students, parents, teachers, and municipalities, facilitated context-specific solutions. Notable outcomes included raising awareness of sustainable mobility, changing mobility behaviour, developing small-scale infrastructure, and highlighting a collaborative approach to mobility challenges.

The experiments have shown that schools can be central hubs for promoting sustainable (school) mobility. Young people can play an important role. Adult participants noted that youth-initiated ideas (e.g. safer pedestrian crossings, improved lighting, adequate sidewalks etc.) address safety concerns and offer good solutions to the challenges of sustainable school mobility. A parent stated, *“In fact, the children’s ideas turned out to be very good suggestions for the adult world”* [BG04, Parents, Women/girls]. In addition, a teacher observed, *“When students are directly involved, they take ownership, which makes the changes more impactful and sustainable”* [IE02, Teachers, Women/girls]. The young people also saw the benefit of being involved in such projects. One participant noted, *“When we are directly involved in a project... we learn about things we wouldn’t normally discuss in daily conversations”* [PT04, Young people, Men/boys].

A recurring insight was the need to educate parents on the importance of sustainable mobility and to involve them in these types of initiatives. One teacher commented: *“Parents often prioritise convenience, saying ‘it’s only five minutes by car’, but this takes away children’s autonomy”* [PT07, Teachers, Women/girls]. Furthermore, ideas for involving parents or entire families were also discussed in the experiments. This included family-oriented events to involve parents in activities and promote sustainable school mobility. For example, a teacher in Bulgaria suggested organising events, such as weekend family competitions, where parents and children could participate together in activities like rollerblading or cycling challenges. These activities could provide

a valuable opportunity to engage families in sustainable mobility initiatives in an interactive and participatory way.

The experiments successfully involved different stakeholders, including young people, parents, teachers from different schools, as well as architects, policy makers and mobility experts, to address various aspects of sustainable urban mobility. This collaboration ensured that different perspectives were included in the decision-making process and in the development of solutions and policy recommendations. These efforts helped discuss different views on challenges to sustainable (school) mobility, address infrastructure issues and improve accessibility. In some cases, schools also took the initiative to integrate sustainable mobility topics into classroom discussions, ensuring that young people actively engaged with the issues.

Young people as change agents

Young people were identified as key drivers of behavioural and cultural change. Their enthusiasm for hands-on activities, such as constructing periscopes, mailboxes or organising mobility games underscored their potential to influence peers and families. Engaged young people can influence their families and peers, amplifying the reach of the experiment. By involving students in Urban Mobility Labs, the message extends to parents, creating a multi-generational impact. As one participant noted, *“The more people [take] part, the better the results will be, because more people will tell their families and friends”* [PT08, Young people, Women/girls]—highlighting the cascading effect of youth-driven advocacy.

The experiment also leveraged practical and modern tools like art and digital media to amplify awareness, with participants suggesting competitions and digital campaigns. As one student emphasised, *“Young people are now very connected to the internet, so maybe you could also post some things on the internet, to see if it attracts attention and brings more young people to the project.”* [PT08 Young people, Women/girls].

Innovative solutions

During the experiments various innovative and impactful solutions were developed, aiming at promoting sustainable mobility and raising awareness. Students identified issues and proposed infrastructure changes, such as painting pedestrian crossings in safer locations and advocating for new bike lanes and school bus routes. During the experiments, awareness-raising activities were also carried out, including bike rides, health walks and the Sustainable Mobility Tree game. These events encouraged walking, cycling, and other sustainable travel modes while fostering enthusiasm among young people. The young people developed innovative solutions like mailboxes for collecting mobility improvement ideas, posters, they built periscopes and composed songs. These solutions were shared within schools and communities, promoting young people’s engagement and ownership of the project.

Youth empowerment

The experiments empowered youth participation, as young people engaged directly with adults, presenting ideas and seeing their voice counted. This strengthened their sense of agency and motivated them to participate in future initiatives. *“...they also are learning how to communicate and cooperate with adults, and how to listen to others... they have grown up, they have become more self-confident, they have become braver... now they are able to have discussions with adults”* [LT10, Parents, Women/girls]. In addition, sharing ideas encourages students to reflect, empathise with their community, communicate effectively, and express themselves creatively. *“Also, these ideas that they are sharing... it makes them think, it makes them empathetic to the way of life in their neighbourhood, the way of communicating in school, being able to convince other students of the benefits of change”* [BG04, Teachers, Women/girls]. In addition to fostering collaboration and promoting sustainable practices, Urban Mobility Labs also strengthen the empowerment of young people.

Inclusivity

The importance of involving young people from different backgrounds and schools was emphasised to ensure equitable participation and inclusivity. This was seen as critical for promoting equity and enabling all members of society to benefit from sustainable mobility. One participant stated: *“Involving less favoured students adds immense value to the project. It gives them the opportunity to experience contexts that are often common for their peers but new for them”* [PT07, Teachers, Women/girls]. This approach also helped to position the school as a social equaliser, bridging gaps between students (e.g. socio-economic or migration status). For example, it has been suggested that free or subsidised school buses should be provided to ensure that young people from disadvantaged areas have safe and convenient access to school without additional financial burden.

Co-creative multigenerational approach

The experiments acknowledged the importance of involving different actors—not just young people but also their parents, families and professionals. A multigenerational approach is crucial for the long-term success of sustainable mobility initiatives, as it ensures that behaviour change and awareness spread across different age groups, creating lasting cultural shifts. *“It’s not just about the students – parents, teachers, and the wider community must be part of the conversation to make real progress”* [IE03, Young people, Women/girls] This emphasises the need for shared responsibility. Sustainable change is most effective when multiple generations work together, ensuring continuity and a broader reach. In this context, co-creation offers the opportunity to share different perspectives and challenges across generations and to work together to solve them. This collaboration also fosters intergenerational learning, where older generations share experiences about past mobility patterns, while younger people introduce modern solutions such as digital tools and new transport technologies.

Furthermore, by involving different age groups, sustainable mobility practices become deeply embedded in social institutions (like values and norms), increasing the chances of long-term changes. A long-term shift requires communities to see sustainable transport as a shared responsibility, passed from one generation to the next. *“Social changes are not imposed; they are embraced. We must teach children from a young age to adopt sustainable mobility habits, just as we did with recycling. Cities that are advanced in sustainable transport did not change overnight – it is a gradual process that must be passed from one generation to the next”* [PT05, Teachers, Men/boys].

Young people as multipliers

Engaging young people in Urban Mobility Labs has a ripple effect on their friends and families, influencing parents and even grandparents. When young people learn about sustainable transport at school, they bring this knowledge home. Parents start considering alternatives, and eventually, entire families adopt greener mobility choices. As one participant noted *“I think it was really useful, especially for me, because when I talked to my parents about the project, they... also changed. We now have our own garden with organic vegetables in the village and I think this project is impacting not only us and the children, but also the adults”* [BG09, Young people, Women/girls].

4.2. Recommendations for fostering sustainable mobility projects in schools

Our analysis shows that co-creative interventions in schools, such as Urban Mobility Labs, can bring about changes in ‘collective action, thinking and feeling’ towards sustainable mobility. The following recommendations are formulated for stakeholders planning activities to promote sustainable mobility in schools. For others looking to design and implement interventions in schools, our experiments offer numerous actionable insights and recommendations that can serve as a blueprint. Below are some key takeaways, which are also presented as a ‘Quick Guide’ on page 24.

Engage stakeholders early and build collaborative partnerships

Successful sustainable school mobility projects require the commitment of all involved institutions, including schools, municipalities, and other partners. Ensuring that these stakeholders are motivated and engaged is crucial. Multidisciplinary teams, including architects, decision-makers, urban planners, mobility experts, etc. can provide valuable insights into behavioural change and infrastructure development. Actively involving students is equally important, as their ideas and enthusiasm can drive innovative solutions while fostering a sense of ownership and long-term impact. Strong partnerships with local authorities ensure that school mobility projects align with broader urban planning and policy goals. Co-operation with municipal leadership is essential for long-term strategies and sustainable practices, providing continuity and institutional support.

Address timing and logistics

To maximise participation, experiment activities should be carefully planned around school schedules, avoiding conflicts with vacations, exams, or other major events. Effective coordination has been shown to improve engagement, as seen in one case where a school that initially struggled to participate was able to organise additional forums, leading to an even better outcome. Flexibility in planning is also essential, allowing room for delays and unforeseen circumstances. In many countries, a Spring-centred timeline may be ideal, as it enables greater involvement in outdoor activities.

Foster inclusivity

Ensuring accessibility for all students, particularly those from different backgrounds or marginalised groups, is key. Addressing financial and logistical barriers, such as providing free transport or necessary resources, can enhance participation. Infrastructure should be designed with accessibility in mind, incorporating features like ramps, tactile paving, and wide pavements, along with inclusive communication methods such as sign language or visual aids.

Prioritise practical and localised solutions

Every community has unique needs, and interventions should be tailored accordingly. Pilot projects can help test and refine strategies before full-scale implementation. Monitoring results and incorporating local feedback ensures that solutions remain effective and relevant.

Build communication and awareness campaigns

A strong communication strategy is essential for engagement. Digital tools, such as social media, can be leveraged to reach young audiences, with relatable stories and public figures amplifying impact. Practical, hands-on awareness activities – such as step challenges, cycling lessons, and inter-class competitions – make sustainability tangible and engaging. While digital outreach is useful, direct, face-to-face interactions with stakeholders are equally important in building trust and ensuring that key messages are effectively communicated.

Integrate sustainability into education

Embedding sustainability in school curricula is an effective way to raise awareness and encourage long-term behavioural change. Dedicated school hours, such as Citizenship classes, can be used to discuss sustainable mobility, while teachers play a crucial role in supporting these initiatives and incorporating related topics into their lessons.

Foster behavioural and cultural change

Encouraging sustainable mobility habits from an early age can lead to lasting behavioural shifts. Promoting walking, cycling, and public transport use in primary schools helps normalise these practices over time. However, changes should be introduced gradually to prevent resistance and build trust. Sudden, imposed measures are less effective than progressive steps that allow communities to embrace new habits organically.

Evaluate initiatives

Setting clear goals and performance indicators helps track the success of interventions, refine strategies, and provide evidence for securing funding or further support. Sharing results through reports, presentations, and public forums not only demonstrates impact but also inspires replication in other schools or municipalities.

Promote long-term sustainability

For lasting impact, policymakers should be encouraged to institutionalise successful interventions within municipal strategies. Empowering students, parents, and local communities to take responsibility for maintaining changes – such as preserving infrastructure and continuing awareness campaigns – ensures that progress is sustained beyond the initial project phase.

Quick Guide to Sustainable School Mobility Projects

1

Engage stakeholders early and build collaborative partnerships

- Select committed partners
- Involve diverse experts
- Engage young people as agents of change

2

Address timing and logistics

- Plan around school schedules
- Develop a flexible timeline
- Spring may be a good time for outdoor activities

3

Foster inclusivity

- Target disadvantaged communities
- Adapt for disabilities
- Involve families

4

Prioritise practical and localised solutions

- Tailor interventions to the community's needs.
- Pilot small-scale projects and adapt based on feedback.

5

Build communication and awareness campaigns

- Use digital tools
- Organise awareness activities
- Use face-to-face communication

6

Integrate sustainability into education

- Embed into curricula
- Encourage teachers to support initiatives

7

Collaborate with municipalities

- Partner with local authorities
- Municipal leadership critical for long-term strategies and practices.

8

Foster behavioural and cultural change

- Promote habits like walking, cycling, and public transport from a young age
- Focus on gradual implementation

9

Evaluate initiatives

- Monitor and evaluate progress
- Disseminate findings to inspire replication and secure support

10

Promote long-term sustainability

- Involve policymakers and encourage institutionalisation of successful interventions
- Empower communities to maintain changes and campaigns

4.3. Policy recommendations

The following policy recommendations (also outlined in the Executive Summary) are based on the experiences and findings of the social experiments on Sustainable Mobility and focus on promoting sustainable mobility in schools; improving infrastructure; and designing mobility policies to support the transition to sustainable mobility in line with the European Green Deal.

4.3.1. Recommendations for promoting sustainable mobility within schools

Integrate sustainable mobility into lessons and curricula

Embedding mobility topics into school curricula through subjects like Citizenship or Environmental Science, helps encourage long-term behavioural change. Schools should facilitate active learning experiences such as competitions, workshops, and field projects that engage students in real-world sustainability challenges. Include awareness-raising initiatives to challenge and transform institutional norms and values around mobility, fostering long-term cultural change.

“What is lacking in the school itself [to] encourage pupils to move more, to live healthier, to come to school differently... is definitely a lack of knowledge. I think we should dedicate one lesson purely for this topic.” [LT07, Young people, Women/girls]

Support school mobility projects

Supporting sustainable mobility among students is essential for fostering healthier lifestyles and reducing environmental impact. Additionally, supporting student-led mobility initiatives help raise awareness and boost engagement, making sustainable mobility a more appealing choice. Implementing programs like ‘Walk-to-School’, cycling campaigns, and step challenges can encourage students to incorporate more physical activity into their daily routines, and experts can be invited to visit and contribute.

“... they need funding for that, because schools do not have money themselves to invite experts from outside. But again, if the municipality will support this idea and if they see an interest and if they think that it’s useful, maybe they can help somehow.” [LT, Local partners, Women/girls]

4.3.2. Recommendations for sustainable mobility infrastructure

Enhance safe and sustainable infrastructure

Investments in pedestrian and cycling infrastructure around schools – including wider sidewalks, protected bike lanes, and improved street lighting – can make active travel a safer and more attractive option. Traffic-calming measures, such as lower speed limits in school zones, further enhance road safety.

“There’s no real way to solve the issue – but there’s ways to make it safer and easier. And maybe that’s what should be prioritised, safety.” [IE09, Young people, Men/boys]

Optimise public and school transport systems

Collaborate with public transport providers to improve accessibility by ensuring well-connected routes, affordable fare structures, and safe, convenient transit options for students. Enhance coordination between schools and transport authorities to align schedules with school start and

end times, reducing waiting periods and overcrowding. Promote subsidised or discounted fare programs for students to encourage greater use of public transit.

“If school buses are to be used, they should be made to cover more schools, more children.” [BG04, Parents, Women/girls]

Improve accessibility and inclusion

Sustainable school mobility must be equitable. Ensure that all students, especially those from socially disadvantaged families, have access to sustainable transport (e.g. by subsidising school buses). Infrastructure improvements, including wheelchair-accessible paths, tactile paving, and safer pedestrian crossings, are essential to making mobility inclusive for all.

“Making the school bus transportation free [or] capping it so that even if you’ve got four kids on the bus, it’s going to be capped at a reasonable price. And when you think of what it saves you in time and fuel, it’s just huge.” [IE11, Parents, Women/girls]

4.3.3. Recommendations for wider policy on school mobility

Foster co-creative multi-generational engagement

Sustainable school mobility efforts are most effective when they involve students, parents, and the wider community (friends, classmates, family members, administration members, professionals etc.). Organising family-oriented activities and fostering dialogue between generations can create lasting cultural shifts in mobility behaviour. Supporting youth participation in decision-making processes strengthens their sense of ownership and responsibility toward sustainable mobility.

“I think that not only young people, and older people, everybody should be involved... I think everybody from 7 upwards should be involved, because that is how we fix our city, which is very beautiful, but when it is polluted with all this gas and cars, you don’t see that beauty.” [BG05, Young people, Women/girls]

Promote sustainable mobility through legal and regulatory frameworks

Establishing clear legal frameworks and municipal policies is essential to support and incentivise sustainable mobility modes such as walking, cycling, and public transport for school commutes. Resources should be allocated to develop infrastructure and programs that encourage sustainable mobility, including safe cycling routes, pedestrian-friendly school zones, and accessible public transport options. Strengthening regulations to limit car traffic around schools, enforcing low-emission zones, and prioritising sustainable transport modes in urban planning are crucial steps in fostering a greener mobility culture. Collaboration between schools, municipalities, and mobility organisations ensures the long-term viability and effectiveness of sustainable mobility initiatives.

“... pedestrians should always come first, because we are doing a good thing, and those who drive should come second.” [LT02, Young people, Men/boys]

Raise awareness and visibility of sustainable mobility

Raising awareness about sustainable school mobility is crucial for encouraging long-term behavioural change. Public awareness campaigns should highlight the benefits of sustainable school mobility choices, emphasising environmental, health, and community advantages. Utilising social media, student-led advocacy, and community events can amplify these messages, making sustainable mobility more visible and engaging. By fostering a culture of shared responsibility, these initiatives help integrate sustainable travel practices into everyday school life.

“I think raising awareness, so that we can all contribute towards more sustainable mobility and change our behaviour—I think that’s quite important!” [PT02, Young people, Women/girls]

Demonstrate concrete actions and commitment

Sustainable school mobility initiatives must lead to tangible results, as visible progress is the main driving force for young people to engage and take an active role in such projects. Implementing concrete measures demonstrates commitment and reinforces the impact of sustainability efforts. When students see real changes in their daily school journeys – whether through safer routes, better infrastructure, or enhanced transport options – they are more likely to stay motivated and advocate for further improvements.

“I would tell a politician... just do something – even if it’s the smallest thing on the list. Work towards it, because great results will come, but something has to actually change, just give it a push.” [IE09, Young people, Men/boys]

5. Conclusions

The mobility social experiments of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project focus on school mobility and its underlying social institutions ('meso phenomena'). Through local Urban Mobility Labs in schools, we have attempted to intervene in these institutions (including norms and values), in order to support the Green Deal objective of 'accelerating the transition to sustainable and intelligent mobility' in the context of school travel.

Overall, our analysis shows that interventions or changes in 'common acting, thinking and feeling' are possible through the development of context-specific mobility strategies in Urban Mobility Labs in schools. Although the implementation of Urban Mobility Labs in schools and the involvement of different groups is seen as a challenge by some local partners, all respondents consider initiatives with future generations to be a very important component for initiating and achieving changes towards more sustainable school mobility.

On the question of changes in social institutions, including values and norms, as a result of Urban Mobility Labs in schools, the picture is at early stages. On the one hand, respondents in all locations reported changes towards sustainable mobility through the development of context-specific mobility strategies. This suggests that developing context-specific mobility strategies in school Urban Mobility Labs can change social institutions, i.e. the way certain social groups act, think and feel together. On the other hand, when looking at the long-term influence of the Urban Mobility Labs on cultural change and the institutionalised values and norms that underlie school mobility, an evaluation beyond the duration of the experiments would be necessary.

In general, our data makes it clear that 'institutionalised norms and values in society' (meso phenomena) represent a major challenge for sustainable school mobility, which will not be easy to overcome in the short term. Furthermore, institutional norms and values such as 'car culture' are inscribed not only in individual practices (micro phenomena) but also in the material environment, such as the urban mobility system and the school system. Thus, a change in school mobility and the underlying institutional values and norms is not possible without a change in the infrastructure or material environment (macro phenomena). What role Urban Mobility Labs in schools and co-creation methods can play in this transition to sustainable school mobility and the achievement of Green Deal targets should be further explored.

Overall, by engaging young people and other stakeholders, the Urban Mobility Labs in schools successfully cultivated a shared understanding of the environmental and social benefits of sustainable mobility. Key recommendations emerged to guide future interventions. To accelerate the transition to sustainable mobility in alignment with the European Green Deal, schools must integrate sustainable mobility principles into their curricula and daily activities. By incorporating mobility topics into school subjects, students develop a long-term awareness of sustainable transport options. Schools should also implement active learning experiences such as workshops, competitions, and student-led projects that engage young people in real-world sustainability challenges.

Beyond education, infrastructure improvements play a crucial role in making sustainable mobility a viable option. Investments in pedestrian- and cyclist-friendly infrastructure – such as protected bike lanes, wider sidewalks, and improved lighting – enhance safety and accessibility. Public transport should be optimised to better serve students by ensuring well-connected routes, aligning schedules with school hours, and providing affordable fares. Additionally, inclusivity must be

prioritised, ensuring that sustainable mobility is accessible to all students, regardless of background, gender or ability.

Finally, effective policies and community engagement are essential for fostering a lasting cultural shift in mobility behaviour. Schools, municipalities, and transport authorities must collaborate to implement clear legal frameworks, allocate resources for sustainable mobility projects, and introduce regulations that limit car traffic near schools. Public awareness campaigns, student advocacy, and family-oriented activities help normalise eco-friendly travel choices and reinforce collective responsibility. Most importantly, taking concrete action—such as improving infrastructure and involving students in decision-making—ensures that sustainability efforts translate into visible progress, motivating young people to embrace and advocate for long-term change. The co-creative involvement of young people and other key stakeholders can make an important contribution to this change and can also promote the empowerment of young people.

6. Acknowledgements

This research was supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036640. Social sciences & Humanities for Achieving a Responsible, Equitable and Desirable GREEN DEAL (SHARED GREEN DEAL) is a €5m EU investment, coordinated by Anglia Ruskin University (UK).

We are grateful for the critical role that ICLEI (Javier Bujeda, Eliane Nemoto) played in the design and implementation of our four experiments, as well as the review of this report too. Similarly, we are incredibly thankful for the fantastic and efficient work done by the local partners themselves (Desislava Todorova and Antonia Shalamanova of the Sofia Development Association, Paul O' Donnell of Am Meitheal Rothar, Lina Gelaziene and Vaiva Ramanauskiene of the Environmental Centre for Administration and Technology, and Filipa Corais of Braga Municipality) in implementing the experiments and in collecting the interview data too. Specifically, thanks to the the Advisory Board members (Paul Curtis, Xenia Dimitrios, Raphaela Kogler, Csaba Orosz) of the SHARED GREEN DEAL sustainable mobility stream. Finally, sincere thanks to all participants for kindly and actively participating in our experiments. This report was reviewed and edited by Rosie Robison and Sarah Royston (Anglia Ruskin University).

7. References

- Bulkeley, H., Broto, V., and Edwards, G. (2014). *An Urban Politics of Climate Change*. Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315763040-20>.
- European Commission, EC (2019) 'The European Green Deal', COM (2019) 640 final, URL: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/european-green-deal-communication_en.pdf (last access: 04.07.2022).
- European Commission, EC (2021) 'The New EU Urban Mobility Framework', COM (2021) 811 final, URL: https://transport.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-12/com_2021_811_the-new-eu-urban-mobility.pdf (last access: 04.07.2022).
- Foulds, C., Truninger, M., Aggeli, A., Crowther, A., & Robison, R. (2025). The Meso Multiple in energy and climate research: How different Social Sciences treat the in-betweenness between the micro and macro. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 119, Article 103910. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2024.103910>.
- Franta, L., Dangschat, J.S., Haufe, N. (2018) 'D2.2 Mobility Labs in Practice. Implementing Neighbourhood Mobility Labs', https://www.rupprecht-consult.eu/fileadmin/migratedRupprechtAssets/Documents/SUN_D2.2_Mobility_Labs_in_Practice_final.pdf (last access: 14.03.2025).
- Haufe, N. and Franta, L., (2020) 'Co-Creation and Sustainable Urban Planning: Who Co-Creates Sustainable Mobility Solutions at the Neighbourhood Level? Experiences from the Horizon 2020 Project "Sunrise"', Aachen: REAL CORP 2020: Shaping Urban Change Proceedings/Ta-gungsband 15-18 September 2020, pp. 163-174.
- Healey, P., (1992) 'Planning through debate: The communicative turn in planning theory', *Town Planning Review* 63 (2), pp.143-162.
- Horelli, L., (1998) Creating child-friendly environments: case studies on children's participation in three European countries. *Childhood*, 5(2), 225-239.
- Kovács, K., Gray, E., Fahy, F., Jost, C., Maussen, J., Rohse, M., Ruiz Ocampo, H., Katusic Cuentas, V., Foulds, C., Noreña Ospina, M., Wieser, P., Haufe, N., Bujeda Erauskin, J., Nemoto, E., Gritti, V., Silvestri, G., Mourato, J., Paliogiannis, H., Roniotes, A., 2024. *SHARED GREEN DEAL Case Study Guides*. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL.
- Mayring, P. (2014) *Qualitative content analysis: theoretical foundation, basic procedures and software solution*, Klagenfurt, <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:0168-ssoar-395173>
- Mayring, P. (2015) *Qualitative Inhaltsanalyse. Grundlagen und Techniken*, Weinheim: Beltz.
- McKoy, D., Eppley, A. and Buss, S. (2022) 'Planning cities with young people and schools: forging justice, generating joy', New York, NY: Routledge, Taylor and Francis Group.
- Rageth, L., Caves, K.M., Renold, U. (2021) Operationalizing institutions: a theoretical framework and methodological approach for assessing the robustness of social institutions, *International Review of Sociology* 31, 507-535. DOI: 10.1080/03906701.2021.2000067.
- Risse, T. (2004) 'Global governance and communicative action'. *Government and Opposition*, 39(2): 288-313; Coafee, J. and Healey, P. (2003) 'My voice: my place: tracking transformations in urban governance'. *Urban Studies*, 40(10): 1979-99.
- Ritzer, G. (2006) 'Institution', in: Scott, J. (Ed.), *Sociology: The Key Concepts*. Routledge, Taylor and Francis Group, New York, NY, pp. 90-97.

Appendix – Methods

A1. Data collection

Qualitative interviews were conducted at the 4 sites, which fed into this report. In total, 46 interviews were conducted. Of these, 42 interviews were conducted with participants in the experiments, i.e. young people (individually or in pairs) and adults (e.g. parents and teachers). These interviews were conducted by our local partners (Galway: Am Meitheal Rothar; Braga: Municipality of Braga; Panevėžys: ECAT; Sofia: SDA). Four additional interviews were conducted with local partners, i.e. the facilitators of the experiments at each location. These interviews were conducted by the corresponding consortium partners of the SHARED GREEN DEAL mobility stream (Galway was interviewed by ICLEI; Braga was interviewed by MRI; Panevėžys and Sofia were interviewed by TUW). The interviews with the participants were conducted face-to-face and in the local language (the final transcripts analysed were translated versions in English). The interviews with the local partners were conducted online and in English. The interviews took place between March and May 2024. A total of 56 people were interviewed, 32 young people and 24 adults (parents, teachers and local partners) (see Table 2.5 in Section 2.5).

The initial intention was that a total of 40 interviews were to be conducted with the participants at the four locations – 10 at each location. It was expected that across these 10, 6 interviews would be with young people (single or in pairs) and 4 interviews with adults, which should include parents (at least 1) and professionals (at least 1). This should result in a total of around 10 hours of interview time.

In practice, the interviews lasted between 13 and 95 minutes. In Braga and Galway, some interviews were slightly short, so an increased number (11) interviews were conducted with participants of the experiments in these two locations. Overall, an interview time of between 7.25 and 9.5 hours was achieved in each location. Participants were interviewed consistently by the local partners according to the interview guidelines, so that the total interview time achieved in all locations did not pose a problem for data quality. Table A.1a shows the number of interviews and interview duration per experimental location.

Table A1.a. Number of interviews and interview duration per experimental location.

Experiment location	Number of interviews	Total interview duration (sum of the interviews)	Minimum interview duration	Maximum interview duration
Braga, Portugal	12	7hrs, 14mins, 55secs	28mins, 23secs	58min, 00secs
Galway, Ireland	12	7hrs 15mins 8secs	13 mins 29 secs	95mins 09 secs
Sofia, Bulgaria	11	8hrs, 41min, 3secs	34mins, 13secs	60mins, 00secs
Panevėžys, Lithuania	11	9hrs, 28mins, 34secs	45min, 01secs	71min, 0secs

In all locations at least 6 young people and 4 adults, including at least one parent and one professional, were interviewed. Only in Panevezys were all the young people interviewed individually, in the other sites some paired interviews also took place with the young people. The young people interviewed were aged between 10 and 18.

A target criterion for the selection of interviewees was actual participation in at least three of the eight experimental activities (forums). This was possible for all interviewees in Braga. In Sofia and Galway this criterion was not met by two interviewees. In Panevėžys, this criterion was not met by one respondent. However, during the selection process, care was taken to ensure that the interviewees were fairly familiar with the topic and the experiment as a whole. Therefore, we believe that these interviewees accurately reflect the participants in the social experiments at each location. Our selection of participants also prioritised gender balance (i.e. at least 40% not men/boys, with a target of 50%). Slightly more women/girls than men/boys were interviewed across all locations, reflecting the gender representation of participants in the experiment (see table 2.5 in section 2.5). Table A1.b shows interviewee characteristics in each experiment location.

Table A1.b. Interviewee characteristics in each experiment location.

Experiment location	Interviewees not involved in min. 3 forums	Young people interviewed individually or in pairs	Age of young people	Adults (min. 1 parent and 1 sectoral professional)
Braga, Portugal	-	3 individually 3 set of pairs	12-17	1 parent 5 professionals
Galway, Ireland	2	5 individually 2 sets of pairs	13-18	2 teachers 2 professionals
Sofia, Bulgaria	2	4 individually 2 sets of pairs	10-12	2 parents 2 professionals
Panevėžys, Lithuania	1	6 individually 0 sets of pairs	11-14	1 parent 3 professionals

The open access interview data is available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15325897>.

A2. Coding process

The collected data was analysed by drawing on Mayring's (2014, 2015) approach to Qualitative Content Analysis (QCA). Following a clear step-by-step procedure, the QCA framework provides a "systematic, rule-bound" (Mayring 2014, p.39) approach for the interpretation of latent meaning in textual material (e.g. interview transcripts, public documents, notes, minutes).

For the data analysis undertaken here, we focused on the QCA aspect of "inductive category development" (Mayring 2014, p.80f.), which describes the iterative process of reducing the content of the material and building a category system (see Figure A2). Though the QCA approach conceptualises a full reduction and paraphrasing of the whole material generated, Mayring also acknowledges that a more selective procedure is viable for larger amounts of data (Mayring 2014, p.79). We thus concentrated this procedure of inductive category development on material relevant to answering the stated research questions.

Figure A2. Steps of inductive category development. Source: Mayring 2014, p.80.

As per this QCA approach, the analysis began with a literature review, which provided initial ideas for the interview guide. The development of an initial category system began with a separate coding exercise by TU Wien (TUW) and Metropolitan Research Institute (MRI). Here, TUW and MRI coded at least two interviews with different groups of people (e.g. young people, stakeholders; subcontractors) in this initial coding exercise. In the next phase, the first category system was then applied and adapted to 12 of the 46 individuals in depth interviews. After completion of this 'pilot testing' (Mayring 2014, p.13), all collected data was re-coded using the adapted category system.

MAXQDA software was used for the coding process. To ensure the quality and rigour of the coding procedure, several coders were involved and the results were made available to the interviewers. The categories developed and the associated quotes have been used in sections 3 and 4 of this report.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036640.